

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Annotation: The article analyzes the reforms in the field of physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan and their stages.

Keywords: physical education, sports, world arenas, material and technical base, badminton, chess, checkers, rhythmic gymnastics

From the first years of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, great attention was paid to the development of physical culture and sports as a factor contributing to national development. For these purposes, changes in physical culture and sports have been adapted to the new economic, political, social and cultural conditions of our society.

Reforms in the field of physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan have defined the prospects for the development of the industry. We can divide this period into three periods:

The first period - 1991-2000, during which the relevant laws, Presidential Decrees and resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers aimed at the development of physical culture and sports in the Republic were adopted.

During this period, the organizational framework for the management of physical culture and sports was improved, the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan, sports federations were established. The emphasis on physical culture - fitness, mass sports, national sports and games has increased significantly. The system of material support of physical culture and sports has been further improved, and the foundations of material and technical base have been created.

Covering the second period - 2000 - 2016, this period was also marked by the adoption of special decisions and measures by the leadership of the state for the development of national sports, professional and mass sports, women's and children's sports, national games.

The third period, covering the years after 2017, will include the implementation of specific programs to promote public health in the field of physical culture and sports, the involvement of young people in sports, the formation of national teams with skilled athletes and sports coaches. In order to create additional conditions for the formation of a comprehensively mature and physically healthy generation with a high culture, a number of new normative and legal acts in the field of physical culture and sports have been adopted.

The country has created a broad legal framework for the development of physical culture and sports, public health. On January 14, 1992, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Culture and Sports" was adopted. On May 26, 2000, the second new version of the Law "On Physical Culture and Sports" was adopted. On September 5, 2015, the third new version of the Law was adopted. The law consists of 8 chapters and 47 articles¹. This law envisages wide involvement of the general population, especially youth and women in physical culture and sports, creation of modern mechanisms of state support of physical

¹ Olimpiya bilim asoslari. – T., 2011. – P.139.

culture and sports, improvement of the system of training specialists, formation of modern and effective sports infrastructure, national sports and the establishment of norms aimed at the development of folk games served to make sports an integral part of life.

In the early 1990s, the majority of female students in higher education, or more precisely about 60%, were not involved in physical education and sports (except for girls in stages I and II of higher education)².

1991-1997 World Wrestling Championships, President's Cup International Tennis Tournament, Tashkent Open International Women's Tournaments, as well as Challenger, Futures and Satellite in Fergana, Samarkand, Gulistan, Bukhara and Karshi. international tournaments were held. The country's athletes successfully participated in the 1992, 1996 Summer Olympics and 1994 Winter Olympics for the first time as an independent team³.

Today, more than 50 sports are popular in our country, 30 of which are included in the program of the Olympic Games. As of 2004, there were a total of 63 federations in Uzbekistan for Olympic and non-Olympic sports and national sports⁴.

In 1993, the Gymnastics Federation of Uzbekistan was established and became a member of the International Gymnastics Federation (FIG)⁵.

In our country, special attention has been paid to the restoration, popularization and widespread promotion of national sports and folk games. In 1994, the first Festival of Folk Games was held in Forish district of Jizzakh region. Since then, it has been held regularly, every two years. In 1998, it was renamed the Alpomish National Sports and Games Festival. Along with competitions in folk dances, scientific and practical conferences are held at the festivals. In 1999, the festival of national sports and folk games "Tomaris" was held among women⁶. These games are still loved and played by our people.

The Concept of the State Program for the Development of Physical Culture and Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the organizational, legal and financial basis for the development of physical culture and sports organizations. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of June 6, 2003 "On the organization of a system of continuous sports competitions aimed at attracting schoolchildren and students to sports" and Universiade sports competitions⁷.

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Every year, the population of our country is engaged in mass sports. For example, in 2008 the number of football players increased by 80.6% compared to 1991, and the number of wrestlers increased by 89.8%. In 1991, there were 52 sports in the country, but today more than 65 out of 74 sports are developing in all regions and creating conditions for their

² Azimov H.G., Sobitov Sh.S. Sport fiziologiyasi. – Toshkent, 1993. – P.43.

³ Republican Conference dedicated to the 100th anniversary of the International Olympic Committee. Lecture notes. - Tashkent: UzDJTI Publishing House. 1994. - 211 p.

⁴ <https://qomus.info/encyclopedia/cat-s/sport-federatsiyalari-uz/>

⁵ Morgunova I.I. Gimnastika. – T.: "Ijod-dunyosi", 2017. – B.38.

⁶ Olimpiya bilim asoslari. – T., 2011. – B.143.

⁷ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On the organization of a system of continuous sports competitions aimed at attracting schoolchildren and students to sports." 06.06.2003

⁸ National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. Volume 12 - B.576 - 582.

⁹ <https://qomus.info/encyclopedia/cat-s/sport-federatsiyalari-uz/>

popularization¹⁰.

In short, in recent years, special attention has been paid in our country to the development of women's sports, including the promotion of a healthy lifestyle. In the period of rapid reforms in all spheres of life of the state and society, the improvement of physical culture and sports, in particular, the development of women's sports, is one of the most pressing issues today.

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¹⁰ Olimpiya bilim asoslari. – T., 2011. – B.144.